

Multilinguism in references: A study of the ISTEEX dataset

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Introduction

The *lingua franca* status of English in research is already well established. Rao (2019), for example, highlights the importance of English as a world language and shows how widely it is used in scientific research, business and education. In this paper, we propose to investigate the extent to which the language of an article determines the languages of the papers that are cited, and whether citations to papers written in different languages are distributed in the same way as papers published in those languages. In other words: To what extent are citations to articles written in English predominant in articles written in other languages?

In fact, Moskaleva & Akoev (2019) showed that publications in the native language (other than English) are read and cited less than those in English. Furthermore, the ranking of journals correlates with the proportion of publications in English for multilingual journals.

Other studies have looked at multilingualism in scholarly publishing, going so far as to advocate for linguistic diversity in publications. Di Bitetti & Ferreras (2017) compared abstracts from bilingual journals and found no differences in aspects such as quality and general interest between articles published in English and other languages in these journals. The work of Smirnova & Lillis (2022) is based on a corpus comparing research articles written in Russian with research articles written in English in the following disciplines: philosophy, sociology, and economics. At the macro level, they raise questions about what is considered "citation-worthy" in different geolinguistic contexts and consider the consequences of citation brokerage and knowledge production practices and circulation on a global scale.

The work of Angulo et al. (2021) shows that science based on only one language, especially English, can be a barrier to knowledge transfer that can create biases in the provision of global models. Experience shows that including non-English sources can reduce bias in understanding and enrich scientific knowledge. In terms of innovation, linguists make

arguments for publishing in their own language, as shown in the reflection of Desclés (2013).

Methods

We have processed articles from the multilingual database ISTEEX¹, which provides multilingual and multidisciplinary retrospective collections of the world's scientific literature. While ISTEEX provides over 23 million documents in English (90 %), it also provides resources in over 50 languages.

Choice of languages and dataset

Our dataset contains articles from all languages present in ISTEEX, with more than 100 articles per language. The ISTEEX database contains the documents in several formats, including XML TEI, with references stored in Grobid or refBibs formats. The reference information is not available for all articles. To create our dataset, we sampled 100 randomly selected articles per language from all articles that have references in Grobid or refBibs formats. Russian articles were excluded from the dataset because the quality of the OCR for this language in the database was very poor.

Processing pipeline

For each article, we extracted the list of references and then the title of the article and the title of the journal or conference. We used these titles to detect the language of the reference as follows:

- The titles were concatenated into a single string and processed using the *spacy-langdetect*² python library.
- If the language of the string is detected by the library with a score above 0.8, we assign that language to the reference. Otherwise, we discard the reference.

Results

Table 1 shows the total number of references for the sample of 100 articles for the 9 languages processed. We also show the number and percentage of references whose language was successfully identified (with a score > 0.8).

¹ <https://www.istex.fr/>

² <https://github.com/Abhijit-2592/spacy-langdetect>

Figure 1 presents a Sankey diagram showing the citing languages (on the left) and the cited languages (on the right). We observe that English is by far the largest segment on the right side, which means that the vast majority of articles tend to cite references in English. It is followed by German and French, which are much smaller. References in many other languages have been identified, but the number is small.

Table 1. Number of references per language

Language	Code	Nb refs	Nb refs, score > 0.8	%
Czech	cs	1206	937	77,69 %
German	de	2118	1872	88,39 %
English	en	4949	4528	91,49 %
Spanish	es	2123	2031	95,67 %
French	fr	3512	3309	94,22 %
Latin	la	2436	1428	58,62 %
Dutch	nl	892	788	88,34 %
Polish	pl	1239	1160	93,62 %
Portuguese	pt	2044	1918	93,84 %

Figure 1. Sankey diagram of the citing languages (left side) and the cited languages (right side)

Table 2 shows a heatmap of the number of references per language for each of the 9 languages examined. We observe that the largest number is for English-to-English references, followed by French-to-English references.

		Language of article								
		cz	de	en	es	fr	la	nl	pl	pt
Reference language	cs	22		2						
	de	106	805	192	25	214	62	56	42	164
	en	542	754	3889	1443	2218	279	241	355	1100
	es	4	9	61	392	15	13	2	7	39
	fr	47	19	41	67	735	126	14	24	152
	nl	1	83	3	1	8	5	416	3	2
	pl	7	4	40	2	6	12	1	672	1
	pt	6	8	8	49	8	121	2	2	31
	other	202	190	292	52	105	808	56	53	429

Table 2. Reference language counts

Discussion and Conclusion

The limitations of this study stem from the fact that many factors can influence the decision to cite a reference in a particular language. For example, the editorial requirements of some journals may privilege references in English or require a translation of the title into the language of the journal. Furthermore, disciplinary differences are to be expected and would require a more detailed study. In Table 1 we can see that articles in English tend to have much more references than articles in Dutch, Polish and Czech. This may be due to disciplinary differences, as not all disciplines are equally represented in the ISTE database, and to editorial requirements.

Another limitation of this study is the difficulty of building a multilingual dataset. ISTE is such a dataset, but we have to consider that the coverage of the different languages is arbitrary and of variable quality.

Finally, in our experiment we relied on the output of the *spacy-langdetect* library, but its performance may be suboptimal for some of the languages (e.g. Latin).

We presented a study on a multilingual dataset with publications in 9 languages. We examined the languages of the cited references. The results show an important preference for English references, which is also present in the articles written in other languages.

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